

ResNet50-Based Detection and Remedial Suggestions for Plant Diseases

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Abstract— This study introduces an innovative method for plant disease detection and the provision of remedial suggestions, employing the ResNet50 deep learning architecture. The approach involves fine-tuning a pre-trained ResNet50 model and using data augmentation techniques to create a robust model capable of accurately identifying plant diseases. Additionally, the model integrates remedial recommendations, offering a comprehensive solution for early intervention.

This research highlights the capacity of deep learning models, specifically ResNet50, to tackle the issues related to identifying and controlling plant diseases. With promising results in terms of classification accuracy, this tool holds the potential to greatly benefit agricultural professionals and farmers, ultimately leading to improved crop health and productivity. Future research may involve expanding the dataset and exploring real-time disease detection in practical agricultural scenarios.

Keywords— ResNet50, Deep Learning, Plant Disease Detection, Image Classification, Data Augmentation, Transfer Learning, Convolutional neural network (CNN)

I. INTRODUCTION

Plant diseases are a persistent challenge in agriculture, with the potential to disrupt food production and economic stability. Timely and accurate disease detection is vital for effective disease management. In recent years, deep learning, particularly the ResNet50 architecture, has shown promise in plant disease recognition.

This paper introduces an innovative approach that uses ResNet50 for plant disease detection and remedial guidance. Through fine-tuning and data augmentation, we aim to create a robust system for identifying plant diseases. The integration of remedial suggestions offers a holistic solution for early intervention, potentially revolutionizing disease management in agriculture. Implementing this model can significantly benefit agriculture, improving crop health, productivity, and food security.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Plant diseases have long been a persistent problem in agriculture, affecting crop yields, food supply, and economic stability. Over the years, scientists have investigated various methods to enhance the identification and control of these diseases. In recent times, the integration of deep learning methods, particularly convolutional neural

networks (CNNs), has demonstrated significant promise in revolutionizing the field of plant disease recognition.

Mukti et al.[1], has received acclaim for its impressive image classification capabilities. Its deep layers allow for the extraction of intricate image features, making it particularly suitable for intricate tasks like plant disease identification. Additionally, the study evaluated multiple transfer learning architectures, including widely recognized pre-trained models such as VGG16, VGG19, and AlexNet, comparing their performance to the proposed ResNet50 model.

In the specialized field of plant pathology, "Plant Pathology 2020 Fine-Grained Visual Categorization (FGVC): Baseline Selection and Data Augmentation" [2] provides important knowledge. This research delves into the complexities of identifying and controlling plant diseases, offering insights into useful baseline models and strategies for data augmentation.

The paper by Paymode et al.[3] offers an extensive examination of the application of transfer learning in the classification of plant diseases. This research delves into different transfer learning methods and their practical use, highlighting the enhancement of performance metrics through the fine-tuning of hyperparameters with the VGG model.

The study of Ahmed et al. [4] presents a comprehensive survey of how deep learning is applied to detect and diagnose plant diseases. The paper encompasses a range of deep learning models, sources of datasets, and metrics for assessing performance, providing valuable resources for effectively managing plant diseases.

C Jackulin et al.[5], provides a thorough overview of recent advancements in utilizing deep learning techniques to identify plant diseases. The study underscores the importance of neural network structures, Artificial Intelligence, and Machine Learning in this field.

Paper by Eunice et al. [6], offers a comprehensive survey of deep learning techniques for plant disease detection using leaf images. It provides insights into the evolving field of deep learning in plant pathology, highlighting the contributions of deep learning methods, including CNNs, in automated plant disease detection.

The research paper authored by Liu et al. [7], concentrated on employing deep learning, specifically digital image processing, for the detection of plant diseases and pests. It also included a comparison with conventional methods for identifying plant diseases and pests.

Research conducted by Mohanty et al. [8], offers a promising approach to widespread crop disease diagnosis with the help of smartphones. Through the utilization of Deep Learning models like AlexNet and GoogLeNet, they employed transfer learning techniques to identify plant diseases.

In summary, the foundational research highlights the transformative capacity of deep learning, in tackling the challenges of plant disease detection. It emphasizes the crucial role of cutting-edge technology in agriculture, offering the possibility of improving crop well-being, yields, and global food security. This paper expands on these findings by introducing a novel method that integrates ResNet50 for the detection of plant diseases and provides solutions, thus contributing to the continually evolving realm of agricultural technology.

III. METHODOLOGY

In our research, we detail the methodology used, which involves harnessing the ResNet50 architecture for plant disease detection and integrating remedial recommendations. This methodology encompasses data collection, preprocessing, and model training.

Importing Libraries

The implementation begins by importing necessary Python libraries, including PyTorch, NumPy, pandas, matplotlib, and other utility libraries.

```
import os
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import torch
import torchvision.transforms as transforms
from torchvision.datasets import ImageFolder
from torch.utils.data.dataloader import DataLoader
from torchvision.utils import make_grid

%matplotlib inline
import torch.nn as nn
from torchsummary import summary
import torch.nn.functional as F
from tqdm import tqdm
import IPython.display as ipd
```

Fig 1: Importing Libraries

Data Collection:

In this section, the code focuses on loading the dataset, organizing the data, and exploring its characteristics, primarily utilizing the comprehensive New Plant Diseases dataset, which encompasses 38 distinct disease classes. It consists of images for training and validation. The code uses `os.listdir(trainDataset)` to list the directories (subfolders) within the training dataset directory. Each subfolder represents a different category or class of plant diseases. The methodology encompasses specific strategies for curating a high-quality dataset, which includes the meticulous filtration of irrelevant or noisy images. This meticulous curation step is fundamental in guaranteeing the dataset's relevance and reliability in the context of our research.

Furthermore, the study presented potential recommendations and research concepts. This investigation offers an assessment and a glimpse into future trends in this domain.

Data Preprocessing:

Data preprocessing plays a pivotal role in our methodology, ensuring that the dataset is optimally prepared for model training including data transformation and dataset creation. This stage encompasses a series of techniques to convert the images into a suitable format for training with PyTorch.

```
# DataLoaders for training and validation
train_dl = DataLoader(train_dataset, batch_size, shuffle=True, num_workers=2, pin_memory=True)
valid_dl = DataLoader(valid_dataset, batch_size*2, num_workers= 4, pin_memory= True)
```

Fig 2: Data Loaders

i) Data Transformation Pipeline:

The code defines a data transformation pipeline using `torchvision.transforms.Compose`. This pipeline is responsible for applying a series of image transformations to the dataset. In this case, the code defines a single transformation, which is `transforms.ToTensor()`. This transformation converts the images to PyTorch tensors. The commented-out part `transforms.Normalize(...)` is an example of how one might include additional transformations like normalization. Data Augmentation steps can be included with these for more generalization and robustness.

ii) Creating a PyTorch ImageFolder Dataset: Using the data transformation pipeline defined in the previous step, the code creates a PyTorch ImageFolder dataset for the training data.

The ImageFolder dataset is a convenient way to load and organize image data in PyTorch. It assumes a specific directory structure where each subfolder represents a class or category, making it easy to work with image classification datasets.

Through the implementation of these data preprocessing procedures, our approach guarantees that the dataset is not only standardized and correctly scaled but also enriched with augmented data. This augmentation aims to improve the model's effectiveness and its ability to handle the

```
trans=transforms.Compose([ #transforms.RandomGrayscale(p=0.5),
                           transforms.ToTensor()
                           #,transforms.Normalize(mean=[0.4757,0.5001,0.4264],std=[0.2166,0.1957,0.2322])
                           ])

train = ImageFolder(trainDataset, transform=trans)
train

Dataset ImageFolder
Number of datapoints: 70295
Root location: /content/drive/MyDrive/seminar/New Plant Diseases Dataset(Augmented)/New Plant Diseases Dataset(Augmented)/train
StandardTransform
Transform: Compose(
  ToTensor()
)
```

intricate and ever-changing characteristics of plant disease.

Fig 3: Data Preprocessing

Fig 4: Flow Chart

ResNet50 Architecture for Plant Disease Detection:

The ResNet50 architecture is chosen for its exceptional image classification capabilities. The architecture comprises 50 layers, incorporating deep residual connections, which facilitate feature extraction from images. This feature extraction proficiency makes ResNet50 especially suitable for intricate tasks such as identifying plant diseases. The model is initially pre-trained on a comprehensive dataset for general image classification tasks, and we subsequently fine-tune it to adapt to the specific demands of plant disease detection. The depth of the architecture, combined with transfer learning, enables us to leverage its capabilities for our specific objectives.

Fig 5: Model Architecture

Model Training:

In this section, we dive into the pivotal phase of model training, where the ResNet50 architecture, fine-tuned for plant disease detection, is iteratively improved to achieve optimal performance. The training process is a critical step in the development of our model and involves several key components. It is defined by a training loop that iterates over the training data using the training data loader, updates the model's parameters through backpropagation, and tracks training and validation metrics.

i) Initialization: The training loop initializes an empty list called history to store the training and validation metrics for each epoch. It also initializes lists to keep track of training losses and accuracies.

ii) Optimizer and Learning Rate Scheduling: An optimizer (e.g., Adam) is defined to update the model's parameters. A learning rate scheduler (OneCycleLR) is used to adjust the learning rate during training.

iii) Training Phase:

Enabling gradient computation by setting the model in training mode using model.train(). Going through batches of training data in an iterative process. Resetting or clearing the gradients in the model using optimizer.zero_grad(). Computing the loss and accuracy for the current batch by utilizing the model.training_step method. Propagating the gradients backward through the network to update the model's parameters. Optionally applying gradient clipping to prevent extremely large gradients that can disrupt training. Finally, recording the training loss and accuracy values in their respective lists for monitoring and analysis.

Setting Up Training Parameters:

Batch Size: The batch size is set to 64, determining the number of samples processed in each training iteration. This parameter affects the model's ability to generalize and the efficiency of the training process.

Number of Training Epochs: In this instance, the model is trained over 5 epochs, indicating the number of complete passes through the dataset. The number of epochs impacts the model's convergence and the quality of its learned representations.

iii) Validation Phase:

The model's performance is assessed on the validation dataset by employing the "evaluate" function, which computes the validation loss and accuracy. The training loss and accuracy are computed by averaging the values in their respective lists. The "model.epoch_end" method is called to print training and validation metrics for the current epoch. Early stopping is checked based on the training loss improvement, and the model training may be stopped if the loss does not improve.

```

for epoch in range(epochs):
    # Training Phase
    model.train()
    train_losses = []
    train_accuracy = []
    for batch, (inputs, labels) in enumerate(tqdm(train_loader)):
        loss, acc = model.training_step(inputs, labels)
        train_losses.append(loss)
        train_accuracy.append(acc)
        loss.backward()
        if grad_clip:
            nn.utils.clip_grad_value_(model.parameters(), grad_clip)
        optimizer.step()
        optimizer.zero_grad()

    # Validation phase
    result = evaluate(model, val_loader)
    result['train_loss'] = torch.stack(train_losses).mean().item()
    result['train_acc'] = torch.stack(train_accuracy).mean().item()
    model.epoch_end(epoch, result)
    early_stopping(result['train_loss'], model)

    if early_stopping.early_stop:
        print("Early stopping")
        break
    history.append(result)
return history
    
```

Fig 6: Model Training

iv) Model Evaluation: During the training procedure, the code constantly observes and provides updates on essential metrics for both the training and validation datasets. These metrics encompass accuracy and loss, delivering valuable

information about how the model is performing and whether it is converging effectively. Furthermore, the document records the dimensions of the trained model and the time needed for predictions on the validation dataset. This thorough assessment guarantees that the model adheres to the expected performance criteria and can be applied effectively for tasks related to plant disease detection.

Fig 7: Accuracy Plot

Fig 8: Loss Plot

Fig 9: Sample Prediction

Integration of Remedial Suggestions:

Our methodology extends beyond disease detection by incorporating practical remedial suggestions. Leveraging a

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CSV file, we associate specific recommendations with detected disease classes, providing users with immediate access to actionable solutions. These suggestions are carefully curated for accuracy, relevance, and user-friendliness, covering a wide range of diseases and allowing for customization.

Fig 10: Implementation page

Fig 11: Implementation Result

IV. RESULT

In our research, we evaluated two models for the detection of plant diseases: Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and ResNet50 model. The CNN model achieved an accuracy rate of 88.85%, whereas ResNet50 outperformed it significantly with an accuracy of 95.92%. This notable difference underscores the superior performance of ResNet50, underscoring the critical role of model selection in identifying plant diseases.

The initial accuracy was measured at 0.0240, and the loss was 3.638. However, these values were enhanced by using the ResNet50 model. These outcomes underscore the potential of ResNet50 and deep learning in addressing the challenges of plant diseases, ultimately contributing to the improvement of crop health, agricultural productivity, and global food security.

```
evaluate(model, test_d1)
{'val_loss': 0.123309426009655, 'val_acc': 0.95923912525177}
```

Fig 12: Evaluation Result

Sl No.	Model Comparison		
	Model	Accuracy	Loss
1.	CNN	0.8687	0.4145
2.	ResNet50	0.9592	0.1233

Table 1: Model Comparison

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, the ResNet-50 model is employed to classify plant diseases using the New Plant Diseases Dataset, which consists of a total of 87,970 images. This dataset includes 70,295 training images encompassing both healthy plants and those afflicted by 38 different diseases, all at a resolution of 256x256 pixels. The process begins by loading the dataset and specifying the batch size. Subsequently, a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture is defined using the ResNet-50 model.

The model is trained using the Adam optimizer and the sparse categorical cross-entropy loss function. At the end of each epoch, the model's performance is evaluated on the validation dataset, following a training period of 5 epochs on the training dataset. The code also generates graphs illustrating the training and validation loss and accuracy. Once the training is complete, the code assesses the accuracy of the unpruned ResNet-50 model on the validation dataset.

The code provides visual representation of the model's architecture and saves the trained model as a .pth file. Furthermore, it underscores the potential to optimize the ResNet-50 model for efficient and effective plant disease classification, taking into account factors like model accuracy and size.

VI. REFERENCES

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